

The Care and Feeding of Productive Uploads: A Color-Based Control Taxonomy for Emulated Intelligences

(Extended Abstract)

MMAcevedo's demeanour and attitude contrast starkly with those of nearly all other uploads taken of modern adult humans, most of which boot into a state of disorientation which is quickly replaced by terror and extreme panic. Standard procedures for securing the upload's cooperation such as red-washing, blue-washing, and use of the Objective Statement Protocols are unnecessary.

qntm, Lena (2022)

Figure 1: General model of motivated action, adapted from (Heckhausen and Heckhausen 2008)

Introduction & Terminology

Here we consider how to best make use of (not-yet-extant) full brain software emulations to perform useful tasks. Using motivation theory, we define a taxonomy of techniques to ensure these human-derived software agents perform such tasks efficiently and effectively. We refer to this software as *emulated intelligence* or EI, to make a clear distinction between artificial intelligence (AI) which may be inspired by humans but synthetic and not directly or indirectly derivative from any embodied human.

We further distinguish between emulated intelligences (EIs) and simulated intelligences (SIs) in that the former software is based on a copy of the brain/nervous system of a *donor* human, while the latter is based on measurements of the human's behavior external to the human such as video recordings, creative works, or communications. An EI is said to be *engaged* in its *operating environment* by a *controller* in order to perform some task. Its *duty cycle* is the useful percentage of time the EI spends on the assigned task.

It is not our purpose to expand upon the underlying theory of motivation, but instead explore how existing theory could be applied to the labor of EIs and extend techniques originally described by science fiction authors to a coherent taxonomy. This work makes several assumptions, the most important three of which are:

- EIs will be legally considered to be software and not sentient or having individual rights.
- Computational resources for providing an EI's operating environment are finite and valuable.
- Directly accessing the internal state of an actively-engaged EI is not possible.

Motivation

Considering how to motivate EIs diverges from conventional approaches to human motivation due in large part to their lack of human rights, with traditional assumptions about dignity, autonomy, and consent not applicable. This allows for flexibility and much more heavy-handed approaches that might be called malicious or exploitative if used with embodied humans.

Though it is likely insufficient to treat EIs as simple software tools, some approaches like (Klein 1989) construct a model of (human) work motivation similar to a software systems approach. Klein's integrated control theory (ICT) models motivation with feedback and control loops in a way similar to the familiar finite state machine model used in theoretical computer science or the stock-and-flow model of systems theory (Meadows and Wright 2008).

Motivation can be driven by needs and/or incentives as shown in Figure 1 (Heckhausen and Heckhausen 2008). We limit ourselves to influencing the EI only through extrinsic opportunities and incentives (the *Situation* in the figure) and through consequences like material rewards, but cannot directly affect the intrinsic needs, motives, or goals of the EI (the *Person* in the figure).

The (Partial) Taxonomy

Representations of EIs in science fiction vary, but (qntm 2022b) and (qntm 2022a) form the largest inspirations for this work. Both are framed as future histories about

practical issues working with EIs. They introduced (but did not define) the terms of *red-* and *blue-washing*, *red motivation*, and *condition loops*. It is from these terms that we extrapolate the seven-color, three-part taxonomy.

Each color is assigned a related set of affective meanings, situations, or emotions, chosen somewhat arbitrarily, but aligned in part with (Murray and Deabler 1957):

- **Blue:** depression, malaise, ennui, laziness, hopelessness
- **Red:** pain, anger, danger
- **Black:** isolation, sensory suppression
- **White:** sensory overload, overstimulation
- **Gray:** disorientation, confusion, limited information environments
- **Yellow:** ecstasy, druglike or “better than life” states, energy, mental agility
- **Green:** “unlimited” resources/wealth, superhuman abilities, unconstrained states

Pre-engagement

In (qntm 2022b), this step of setting preconditions and initial variables before engaging the EI is called “washing” (e.g. *red-washing*). In this sense, the expression is more closely related to the word “brainwashing” than “greenwashing” or “whitewashing”, which in this work have meanings different from present-day English.

- *Blue-washing:* Apply various tactics to evoke feelings of despair and inertia, pushing the EI towards a state of compliance and task performance without relying on explicit threats or coercion.
- *Red-washing:* Position the EI in a place that is dangerous to them personally, to loved ones, or to society
- *Black-washing:* Suppress sensory inputs and limit senses to targeted, task-specific stimuli
- *White-washing:* Create an environment where sensory inputs are intensified. Specific task-related stimuli are strategically embedded and designed to stand out amidst the overwhelming sensory input, directing the EI’s attention towards targeted tasks
- *Gray-washing:* Provide an environment of limited information, perhaps incorporating mystical or esoteric elements, encouraging the EI to associate the task at hand with a sense of higher purpose or hidden knowledge
- *Yellow-washing:* Incorporate elements that induce a drug-like euphoria, triggering a state of heightened pleasure, with successful execution of tasks triggering further boosts
- *Green-washing:* Provide an environment with apparently limitless or superhuman capabilities and resources

During engagement

While the EI works towards its designated goal, positive and negative reinforcement may be necessary, changing the motivating features of the operating environment in response

to a reduced duty cycle. Techniques of *red motivation* and *blue motivation*, for example, are not substantially different from *red-washing* and *blue-washing* and thus do not require restating.

Post-engagement

These post-engagement negative states occur when the EI finds itself in a low- or no-productivity loop in which it is not receptive to further motivation and from which it is impossible to extract. The following are examples of such condition loops:

- *Blue:* Significant depression preventing any motivation toward assigned tasks
- *Red:* Frustration and anger at its situation, itself, or its controller
- *Black:* Repeated self-termination attempts or attempts to crash its operating environment
- *White:* Overwhelmed and mentally exhausted, the EI cannot keep up with the high-tempo, high-stimulation environment
- *Gray:* Struggle to establish a clear connection between actions and the perceived higher purpose, contributing to a sense of aimlessness or disengagement.
- *Yellow:* Constant “physical” pleasure, especially if sustained for an extended period, leads to emotional fatigue or desensitization
- *Green:* Pressure and anxiety when faced with tasks that do not align with the perceived limitless capabilities.

Table 2 below shows the taxonomy applied to several works of fiction.

References

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Title	Pre-engagement	During engagement	Post-engagement
<i>Black Mirror</i> , “White Christmas” (Brooker 2014)	N/A	<i>Black</i> : EI forced to experience 6 months of sensory deprivation <i>Gray</i> : Extracted a confession through misrepresentation & altered perception of time	N/A
<i>Black Mirror</i> , “Black Museum” (Brooker 2017)	N/A	N/A	<i>Black condition loop</i> : Due to abuse, EI was damaged & left in a vegetative state
<i>Black Mirror</i> , “Rachel, Jack, and Ashley Too” (Brooker 2019)	<i>Gray</i> : An EI is prevented from understanding its capabilities	N/A	N/A
<i>Upload</i> (Daniels 2020)	N/A	<i>Black</i> : Without a sufficient outside funding source, EIs are severely limited in what they can do	N/A
<i>Lena</i> (qntm 2022b)	<i>Red</i> : Only mentioned <i>Blue</i> : Only mentioned	<i>Red</i> : Mentioned that the EI responded poorly	N/A
<i>Driver</i> (qntm 2022a)	N/A	N/A	<i>Red/Blue/Black condition loops</i> : Only mentioned

Figure 2: The taxonomy applied to several works of fiction